

Evaluation of Ocular Hemodynamic Alterations in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus using Color Doppler Imaging

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetic retinopathy is one of the microvascular problems that is greatly increased by diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic illness. The aetiology of diabetic retinopathy heavily relies on changes in ocular haemodynamics. With a focus on the association between these changes, the length of diabetes, and the existence of diabetic retinopathy, this study used colour Doppler imaging to assess ocular haemodynamic alterations in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study including 150 individuals with diabetes mellitus was carried out. Colour Doppler imaging was used to evaluate ocular haemodynamic parameters such as resistive index (RI), end-diastolic velocity (EDV), and peak systolic velocity (PSV). SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data, and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used.

Results: The mean age of participants was 55.2 years, with the majority being male (56.7%). The mean values for PSV, EDV, and RI were 33.5 cm/s, 10.4 cm/s, and 0.69, respectively. Participants with a diabetes duration of >5 years showed significantly lower PSV and EDV, and higher RI compared to those with a duration of ≤5 years ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, participants with diabetic retinopathy had significantly lower PSV and EDV, and higher RI compared to those without retinopathy ($p < 0.05$). Multivariate regression analysis identified age, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels as significant predictors of PSV.

Conclusion: Significant ocular hemodynamic alterations were observed in diabetic patients, particularly among those with longer disease duration and diabetic retinopathy. These alterations in blood flow parameters may contribute to the development and progression of ocular complications in diabetes.

Recommendations: Regular ocular assessments using color Doppler imaging should be incorporated into the management of diabetic patients, especially those with a longer duration of diabetes and those exhibiting signs of diabetic retinopathy.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Diabetic retinopathy, Ocular hemodynamics, Color Doppler imaging, Peak systolic velocity.

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Introduction

Hyperglycemia, a chronic metabolic disease caused by deficiencies in either insulin action or secretion, or both, is the hallmark of diabetes mellitus. With 463 million affected globally, and that figure predicted to increase to 700 million by 2045, it represents a substantial global health burden [1]. Numerous microvascular and macrovascular problems are linked to the prevalence of diabetes, and these issues significantly increase the morbidity and mortality rates of those who have the disease.

Diabetic retinopathy, the most common cause of vision loss in adults of working age, is one of the major microvascular consequences of diabetes. About one-third of people with diabetes have

diabetic retinopathy, and the risk rises with the length of the condition and inadequate glycaemic management [2]. Diabetes-related retinopathy has a complex pathophysiology that includes oxidative stress, inflammation, and retinal blood vessel damage brought on by hyperglycemia. Additionally, recent research has brought attention to the role that ocular haemodynamics plays

in the onset and development of diabetic retinopathy.

A non-invasive ultrasound method called colour Doppler imaging (or CDI) makes it possible to measure the blood flow velocities in different

vascular beds, including the circulation in the eyes. The CDI measures variables that offer information about the haemodynamic state of the ocular vasculature, including resistive index (RI), peak systolic velocity (PSV), and end-diastolic velocity (EDV) [3]. Changes in these parameters have been linked to diabetic retinopathy, indicating that alterations in ocular blood flow could be involved in the aetiology of this consequence.

Studies have demonstrated that patients with diabetes exhibit significant changes in ocular blood flow, including reduced PSV and EDV, and increased RI, indicating increased vascular resistance [4]. These changes are believed to result from endothelial dysfunction, increased blood viscosity, and microvascular occlusions, all of which are common in diabetes. Moreover, the duration of diabetes and glycemic control have been identified as critical determinants of ocular hemodynamic alterations, with longer disease duration and poor glycemic control associated with more pronounced abnormalities [5].

Given the increasing prevalence of diabetes and its associated complications, it is crucial to understand the ocular hemodynamic changes that occur in diabetic patients. This understanding can aid in the early detection and management of diabetic retinopathy, potentially preventing vision loss.

This study aimed at evaluating ocular hemodynamic alterations in patients with diabetes mellitus using color Doppler imaging.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting

- Study Duration: 2022 to 2023
- Study Place: Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna

Participants

The study included a total of 150 participants diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (Type 1 or Type 2)
- Age 18 years and above

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of ocular trauma or surgery
- Presence of any other ocular diseases (e.g., glaucoma, uveitis)
- Pregnant or lactating women
- Patients with uncontrolled systemic hypertension
- Patients on medications affecting ocular blood flow

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively as they presented to the hospital. Information bias was reduced by standardizing the procedures for data collection and ensuring all investigators were trained uniformly. Confounding factors were addressed through statistical adjustments during the analysis phase.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and medical records review. The questionnaire included demographic details, medical history, and relevant clinical information. Ocular hemodynamic parameters were assessed using color Doppler imaging.

Procedure: The inclusion and exclusion criteria were utilised to determine the eligibility of the participants. Written informed consent was acquired, and participants received comprehensive information regarding the study. An extensive ophthalmic assessment was carried out.

Colour Doppler imaging was used to quantify ocular haemodynamic parameters such as resistive index, end-diastolic velocity, and peak systolic velocity. A pre-made data collection form contained all measurements and pertinent clinical data.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analysed using SPSS 23.0. Participants' demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. Ocular haemodynamic parameters were compared between groups. Inferential statistics like t-tests and chi-square tests assessed the findings' significance. A p-value <0.05 indicated statistical significance. Multivariate regression adjusted for confounders.

Result

There were 150 patients with diabetes mellitus in all in the trial. Table 1 provides an overview of the participants' clinical and demographic features.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants

Characteristic	Total (N=150)	Mean (SD) / n (%)
Age (years)	55.2 (10.4)	
Gender		
- Male		85 (56.7%)
- Female		65 (43.3%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	8.3 (5.1)	

Type of Diabetes		
- Type 1		30 (20.0%)
- Type 2		120 (80.0%)
Presence of Diabetic Retinopathy		65 (43.3%)
HbA1c (%)	7.8 (1.2)	

The ocular hemodynamic parameters measured using color Doppler imaging are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Ocular Hemodynamic Parameters

Parameter	Mean (SD)
Peak Systolic Velocity (cm/s)	33.5 (5.2)
End-Diastolic Velocity (cm/s)	10.4 (2.8)
Resistive Index	0.69 (0.05)

< 5 years and > 5 years were the categories into which the participants were split according to the length of their diabetes. Table 3 displays the comparison of ocular haemodynamic characteristics between different groups.

Table 3: Comparison of Ocular Hemodynamic Parameters Based on the Duration of Diabetes

Parameter	≤ 5 years (n=60)	> 5 years (n=90)	p-value
Peak Systolic Velocity (cm/s)	35.0 (4.8)	32.4 (5.3)	0.002
End-Diastolic Velocity (cm/s)	11.2 (2.6)	9.9 (2.9)	0.001
Resistive Index	0.67 (0.04)	0.70 (0.05)	0.005

The ocular hemodynamic parameters were also compared between participants with and without diabetic retinopathy (Table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of Ocular Hemodynamic Parameters Based on the Presence of Diabetic Retinopathy

Parameter	With Retinopathy (n=65)	Without Retinopathy (n=85)	p-value
Peak Systolic Velocity (cm/s)	31.8 (5.5)	34.7 (4.7)	0.001
End-Diastolic Velocity (cm/s)	9.6 (2.7)	10.9 (2.8)	0.004
Resistive Index	0.71 (0.06)	0.68 (0.04)	0.003

A multivariate regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders, including age, gender, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Multivariate Regression Analysis for Predictors of Peak Systolic Velocity

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error (SE)	p-value
Age (years)	-0.12	0.05	0.02
Gender (Male)	0.56	0.32	0.08
Duration of Diabetes (years)	-0.45	0.15	0.01
HbA1c (%)	-0.28	0.12	0.03

Discussion

This cross-sectional observational study included 150 participants with diabetes mellitus to evaluate ocular hemodynamic alterations using color Doppler imaging. The demographic analysis revealed that the mean age of participants was 55.2 years, with the majority being male (56.7%). Most participants had type 2 diabetes mellitus (80.0%), with an average disease duration of 8.3 years.

The ocular hemodynamic parameters, specifically PSV, EDV, and RI, were measured. The mean values observed were 33.5 cm/s for PSV, 10.4 cm/s for EDV, and 0.69 for RI. When participants were categorized based on the duration of diabetes, those with a disease duration of more than 5 years exhibited significantly lower PSV and EDV, along with a higher RI compared to those with a disease duration of 5 years or less. This suggests that longer

diabetes duration is associated with greater impairment in ocular blood flow.

A comparison based on the presence of diabetic retinopathy showed that participants with retinopathy had significantly lower PSV and EDV, and higher RI compared to those without retinopathy. These findings indicate that diabetic retinopathy, a common complication of diabetes, is associated with significant alterations in ocular hemodynamics, potentially contributing to the progression of retinal damage.

Using multivariate regression analysis, PSV was found to be significantly predicted by age, length of diabetes, and HbA1c levels. In particular, lower PSV was linked to older age, longer diabetes duration, and higher HbA1c levels. This highlights how these variables contribute to diabetic patients' declining ocular blood flow.

Overall, patients with diabetes mellitus exhibit notable alterations in their ocular haemodynamics, especially those who have had the condition longer and have diabetic retinopathy. These changes in blood flow parameters highlight the significance of routine ocular examinations and strict glycaemic control in diabetic patients as they may play a role in the onset and progression of ocular problems in diabetes.

A study used colour Doppler ultrasound to assess the post-ocular haemodynamic alterations in diabetic patients. Sixty normal participants served as controls in the study, while sixty diabetic patients were split into three groups: non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), diabetic no-retinopathy (DNR), and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). The results showed that there were notable variations between the groups in resistance index (RI), peak systolic velocity (PSV), and end-diastolic velocity (EDV). While the PDR group displayed the lowest EDV and PSV and the highest RI, the control group displayed the highest EDV and PSV and the lowest RI. These findings imply that colour Doppler ultrasound is a useful tool for tracking the amount of diabetic retinopathy and retinal blood flow [6].

A review was conducted on the use of colour Doppler imaging to investigate the ocular haemodynamics of diabetic retinopathy in pregnant women. The study highlighted how colour Doppler imaging may be used to evaluate ocular blood flow in pregnant patients at any gestational age and how non-invasive it is. Ocular blood flow characteristics were found to alter, especially as diabetic retinopathy progressed and following anti-VEGF and retinal laser photocoagulation treatments [7].

Using colour Doppler imaging, a study evaluated retrobulbar circulation in 50 type 2 diabetic patients and 50 age-matched controls. The study found that diabetic patients, particularly those with diabetic retinopathy, had notable alterations in the resistivity index (RI) and flow velocities in the central retinal artery (CRA) and ocular artery (OA). When comparing the diabetic groups to the control group, the RI in the OA was significantly greater, suggesting that the diabetic retinopathy is caused by increased vascular resistance and decreased blood flow [8].

A colour Doppler assessment of 73 individuals with diabetes and 73 healthy controls was carried out. The PSV, EDV, and RI of the CRA varied statistically significantly between diabetics and controls, according to the study. The results demonstrated the value of colour Doppler imaging in early diagnosis by indicating that retinal haemodynamic alterations may arise in diabetics even prior to clinical signs of retinopathy [9].

Using colour Doppler imaging, a study examined haemodynamic alterations in retrobulbar blood

arteries in diabetic patients with and without retinopathy. There were notable variations in the RI and flow velocities in the OA, CRA, and short posterior ciliary arteries (SPCA) across the groups in the research, which comprised 50 patients with diabetes and 50 without the condition. The presence and severity of diabetic retinopathy were found to be connected with higher RI values, indicating that these measures may be useful in identifying persons who are more vulnerable [10].

Conclusion

This study identified significant ocular hemodynamic alterations in patients with diabetes mellitus, particularly among those with a longer duration of the disease and the presence of diabetic retinopathy. These changes in blood flow parameters, measured using color Doppler imaging, highlight the importance of regular ocular assessments in diabetic patients. Early detection and management of these hemodynamic alterations may help in preventing the progression of diabetic retinopathy and associated vision loss.

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